

Preliminary experiments on using Generative Large Language Models for Latin Word Sense Disambiguation

Authors: Andrea Farina^a, Iacopo Ghinassi^b, Barbara McGillivray^a

^a *King's College London, Department of Digital Humanities*

^b *Queen Mary University of London, Department of Electronic Engineering and Computer Science*

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This report summarises the results of initial experiments aimed at evaluating the accuracy of Generative Large Language Models (GLLMs) on the task of Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) in Latin.

1. Context

We used 299 text snippets from the annotated dataset for Latin described in McGillivray et al. (2022), which was created as part of the SemEval shared task on Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection (Schlechtweg et al. 2020). For each of 40 Latin lemmas, the original dataset contained 60 text snippets, with 30 randomly selected from BCE texts and 30 from CE texts in the LatinISE corpus (McGillivray & Kilgarriff 2013). The annotation process followed a modified version of the DuReL framework (Schlechtweg et al. 2018). The annotators assessed the degree of relatedness between a usage instance of a target word and each of its possible dictionary definitions using a four-point scale (Unrelated, Distantly Related, Closely Related, and Identical). The definitions were sourced from the Logeion online dictionary (<https://logeion.uchicago.edu/>), incorporating Lewis and Short's *Latin-English Lexicon* (1879), Lewis' *Elementary Latin Dictionary* (1890), and Du Cange's dictionary. An example of the annotation is given in Table 1 (Appendix).

Our experiments focussed on three scenarios:

- A. Categorical sense disambiguation, described in section 2;
- B. Time-sensitive disambiguation, described in section 3;
- C. Graded disambiguation, discussed in section 4.

2. Categorical sense disambiguation

For each of the 299 text snippets, we used ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2023) in a zero-shot setting with the following prompt which is modulated from existing research in the use of ChatGPT for WSD (Kocoń et al. 2023):

- “Given the following sentence¹: ‘[SENTENCE CONTAINING TARGET WORD]’, what is the meaning of the word ‘[TARGET WORD]’ in that context? Choose between {0: ‘[MEANING 1]’², 1: ‘[MEANING 2]’, ... n: ‘[MEANING n]’}. Output the answer as a python list including the key of the correct definition”.

The output consists of a python list, as it is common in LLM literature, so as to enforce output consistency. For instance, to disambiguate the meaning of *honor* in one of the snippets we used the prompt in (1).

- (1) Given the following sentence: “, *Aelfflæda, conloquium perpes reticere memento, Absolver donec vinclis et carcere carnis.; Nec mora, veriloqui complentur in ordine dicta. Ecclesiae iussis, precibus lacrimisque coactus Vatis et ipse genas luctu perfusus amaro Dulcibus extrahitur latebris populisque regendis Praeficitur, modio lateat ne tecta lucerna, Sed iubar alticomum Domini diffundat in aedem. Ecclesiam gemino qui rexit episcopus anno Et priscis properavit ovans se reddere lustris. Utque satisfieret vatis per singula dictis, Sol magnum explevit solitis sub mensibus annum, Pictorum infesto dum doncidit Ecgfridus ense Et Nothus in regni frater successit **honorem**, Scottorum qui tum versatus in incola terris Caelestem intento spirabat corde sophiam, Nam patriae fines et dulcia liquerat arva, Sedulus ut Domini misteria disceret exul. Huius nunc Tyrio venerabile pignus in ostro lure datas patrio sceptri iam tractat habenas, Utque novus losia fideque animoque magis quam Annis maturus, nostrum regit inclitus orbem. Ergo sacerdotis summi fastigia nactus, Mente manu fulget Cuthbertus et ore coruscus Commissosque greges precibus monitisque tuetur. Pauperibus qui dives, inops sibi, blandus amaris, In turbis monachus, neque enim vel tegmina sueta Arida vel heremi” what is the meaning of the word “**honorem**” in that context? Choose between {0: "honor, repute, esteem", 1: "Public honor, official dignity, office, post,"; 2: "anything given as a mark of honor, an honorary gift, a reward"; 3: "a quality that brings honor or consideration, an ornament"; 4: "A magistrate, office-holder"}. Output the answer as a python list including the key of the correct definition.*

Our experiment was performed on target words associated with different POS (nouns, adjectives, verbs). Their distribution varies in relation to how many text snippets are present for each lemma. In total, our sample includes 212 noun occurrences, 52 adjective occurrences, and 35 verb occurrences (Table 1).

¹ We used the word ‘sentence’ instead of ‘text snippet’ to keep the prompt easier for the model.

² The list of meanings is drawn from McGillivray et al. (2022).

POS	NUMBER OF TEXT SNIPPETS	PERCENTAGE
noun	212	70.9%
adjective	52	17.4%
verb	35	11.7%
[TOTAL]	299	100%

2.1. Results

2.1.1. Quantitative analysis

Out of 299 text snippets, one of them was excluded as one annotator in McGillivray et al. (2022) could not decide the meaning of the target word in context (*cohors*), so we did not have data to compare the output of ChatGPT. This means that the prompt in Section 1 was actually used 298 times on the GLLM, and that the overall number of noun occurrences was 211 instead of 212.

Overall, the results given by ChatGPT were identical to the human annotation 180 times (60.4%). Conversely, ChatGPT did not identify the correct meaning of the target word in context 118 times (39.6%). Table 2 summarises these results.

Figure 1: Percentage (white) and absolute number (black) of correctly annotated senses (blue) against incorrectly annotated senses (orange) for all of our samples.

Table 3 provides the performance of ChatGPT with respect to the target words' POS.

Figure 2: percentage of correctly annotated (blue) and incorrectly annotated (orange) senses divided by POS. The numbers inside the bar charts express absolute values.

The accuracy with nouns (60.1%) is almost identical to the average accuracy of the model (60.3%). The accuracy with verbs (54.3%) is below average. The model reaches the highest accuracy with adjectives (65.4%). On the other hand, the model reaches the lowest accuracy with verbs (45.7%), above average (39.6%). One interpretation of this could be that verb semantics is usually more complex than noun semantics, and for this reason the model makes more mistakes in WSD tasks where the target word is a verb. Nonetheless, this hypothesis requires further studies and still needs to be tested at a higher scale, also with the help of broader cognitive studies.

2.1.2. Qualitative analysis and interpretation of the results

In a few cases, ChatGPT was asked to motivate its choice, regardless of whether the output matched with the human annotation or not. The prompt was the following:

- “Give reasons for your choice”.

Consider (2) and (3) below, with two forms of the adjective *acerbus*³.

(2) [*curiae CC marcas argenti ob eam negligentiam, quod ad curiam non venerat nec de terra debitam fecerat fidelitatem. Iuravit quoque Italicam expeditionem. Deinde iuravit,*

³ In this and in the examples below, we give the translation of the sentence including the target word considering part of its left and right contexts. The untranslated part is given in square brackets.

*ut in proxima nativitate Domini ad curiam Magdeburg celebrandam venire deberet, iuxta iudicium et sententiam Polanorum et Boemorum super querimonia fratris sui expulsi plenarie responsurus. Sicque, iurata principi fidelitate, sicut mos est, et de supradictis omnibus fideliter adimplendis acceptis obsidibus, Gazimero videlicet, fratre ducis, et aliis nobilibus, gloriosam adeptus victoriam Deo duce feliciter augustus revertitur.] Ipse tamen dux dolis plenus et **acerbam** dominationis cupidinem mente gerens iamiam suis promissionibus, ut postmodum patuit, moliebatur insidias. [Nam nec ad curiam venit nec sufficientes pro se procuratores misit, Italicam quoque expeditionem violato sacramento mentitus est. Capitulum Non multo post apud Herbipolim civitatem[Alexii] Constantinopolitani imperatoris legati coram principe cum muneribus suam peragunt legationem. Quia tamen verba eorum in quibusdam fastum regalem et Grecum in subornato sermone videbantur sapere tumorem, imperator eos despexit, et nisi in melius commutata sententia commodius sibi prospexissent, si fieri poterat salvo nunciorum privilegio, dissimulationem agente principe, prope fuit.]*

‘[...] Nevertheless, the leader himself, full of deceit and harbouring a bitter desire for domination in his mind, was already plotting treachery through his own promises, as it later became clear [...].’ (Otto of Freising, *Gesta Friderici Imperatoris*, ca.1114-1158 CE)

- (3) [*et in hunc casum extendenda est divi marci oratio et procul dubio et in hac specie audiendus est petitor hereditatis et maneat liberum arbitrium servorum, sive ad libertatem venire volunt sive in servitute remanere.; a-; CJ. a: Imperator Justinianus Licet enim romanam civitatem recusare nemini servorum licet, tamen in hoc casu, ne propter quorundam indevotionem alii maneant in servitute, volentibus quidem omnibus servis licere in libertatem pervenire,] nolentibus autem quibusdam vel recusantibus spontaneam servitute imminere oportet et, quem patronum habere noluerint, dominum suum, forsitan et **acerbum**, sentiant.]; a-; CJ.: Imperator Justinianus Sin vero non omnes libertates adimplere pollicitus fuerit, sed certum numerum servorum ex his, qui ad libertatem venire iussi sunt, melius est, si quidem res hereditariae sufficiunt ad implendos creditores, etiam omnibus servis dare libertatem, etsi hoc non pollicitus est. si autem deest in exsolvendis creditoribus, humanius est, ut saltim pauci veniant ad libertatem.; a-; CJ.: Imperator Justinianus Sed hoc quidem antiquis dubitationibus remedium invenimus. bellissimam autem repletionem praefatae constitutioni donantes sancimus.]*

‘[...] those [slaves] who do not want or refuse [freedom], however, will remain in voluntary slavery, and those who do not want to have a patron may feel the weight of their master, perhaps even a harsh one [...].’ (Emperor Justinianus, *Codex*, 529-534 CE)

In (2), the meaning of *acerbus* is ‘(of things) heavy, sad, bitter’, identified by ChatGPT. In (3), *acerbus* means ‘(of people) rough, violent’, which ChatGPT did not identify, connecting the target word with ‘(of things) heavy, sad, bitter’.

ChatGPT’s replies to the prompt “Give reasons for your choice” for (2) and (3) are given below in (4) and (5), respectively.

- (4) The word "*acerbam*" is used in the context of describing the dux (duke) who, despite swearing allegiance and making promises, harbors a bitter and harsh desire for domination. The use of "*acerbam*" in this context implies a negative and bitter quality

associated with the duke's intentions, aligning with the definition of "(of things) heavy, sad, bitter." The choice reflects the figurative sense of bitterness in the duke's ambitions and actions.

- (5) In the given context, the word "*acerbum*" is used in connection with the phrase "forsitan et acerbum," suggesting that those who refuse or neglect to have a patron might feel the bitterness (*acerbum*) of being in servitude. The use of "*acerbum*" in this context implies a sense of heaviness, sadness, or bitterness associated with the potential consequences of not having a patron, aligning with the definition "(of things) heavy, sad, bitter." The choice reflects the figurative sense of bitterness in the situation described.

In fact, the explanation given for *acerbam* in (4) is reasonable in order to identify the meaning of the word in context. On the other hand, the connection of *acerbum* with *forsitan* in (5) is actually not useful to explain the meaning of *acerbum*, as this is connected to the noun *dominum*. This probably becomes even more interesting after reading (6) below, containing a translation of (3) provided by ChatGPT itself.

- (6) Emperor Justinian: For, although it is not permitted for anyone to refuse Roman citizenship, in this case, so that some do not remain in servitude due to the indifference of others, it is allowed for all willing slaves to attain freedom. However, for those unwilling or resisting, it is necessary to impose spontaneous servitude upon them. And for those who do not wish to have a patron, they may perhaps feel the presence of a master, **even a harsh one**.

In (6), the adjective *acerbum* has been correctly referred to *dominum*. This means that the model is actually capable of grasping the meaning of *acerbum* in context, so it should be able to connect it with the meaning '(of people) rough, violent', as the adjective is referred to a person.

3. Time-sensitive disambiguation

We also checked whether ChatGPT is able to recognise meta-textual parameters such as author, title, date, and language period to enhance disambiguation. To do so, we started from the categorical prompt provided in Section 2, and added meta-textual information after the model did not recognise the meaning of the adjective *beatus* in (7) below.

- (7) [*an sola dei uoluntate et ordinatione hunc discursum immobiliter teneant. Philosophi uero tam eos quam ipsum totum mundum animatos esse astruunt, et quaedam animalia rationalia, immortalia, atque impassibilia non dubitant asserere, dicentes omnem motum in corporibus ab anima incipere, nec uspiam corpus nisi per eam moueri. Qui etiam mundum ita ubique animalibus repleti uolunt, ut singulae mundi partes habeant animalia propria: aer quidam iste inferior et corpulentior usque ad lunam daemones, superior uero pars mundi quam aethereum caelum nominare solemus, planetas uel caetera sidera.*] Quam quidem sententiam **beatus** Augustinus commemorans, libro *De ciuitate dei* VIII, ita de platonicis ait: [Omnium, inquit, animalium in quibus est anima rationalis, tripartita diuisio est: in deos, homines,

daemones. Deorum sedes in caelo est, hominum in terra, in aere daemonum. Item: Habent daemones cum diis communem immortalitatem corporum animarum autem cum hominibus passiones. Et post aliqua descriptionem daemonum ex dictis Apuleii platonici supponens ait: Breuiter Apuleius daemones definiens, ait eos esse genere animalia, anima passiuia, mente rationalia, corpore aerea, tempore aeterna.]

'[...] Indeed, recalling this opinion, the blessed Augustine, in Book 8 of *The City of God*, speaks about the Platonists in these terms: [...].' (Petrus Abaelardus, *Expositio in Hexameron*, 1079-1142 CE)

In this case, *beatus* means 'blessed', as it is part of the phrase *beatus Augustinus* and the text comes from the Christian Medieval Latin. Initially, ChatGPT wrongly interpreted *beatus* as 'rewarded'. However, it was able to identify the correct meaning of the adjective after adding the following prompt:

- "The sentence is from Abaelardus, Petrus, *Expositio in Hexameron*, 1079-1142A.D., cent. 11-12 A. D., prose, Mediaevalis".

In this instance, ChatGPT is able to change the way in which it interpreted word meanings after it was provided with metatextual information.

4. Graded disambiguation

The annotation framework described in McGillivray et al. (2022) follows a graded annotation approach, adapted from the DuReL framework (Schlechtweg et al. 2018-2020). Human annotators assigned meaning(s) to a word instance using a graded scale with the following values: 0 (cannot decide), 1 (unrelated), 2 (distantly related), 3 (closely related), and 4 (identical). In the prompt given in Section 1, ChatGPT is asked to assign only one meaning to the target word. However, can graded annotation be performed with the model? To answer this question, we first gave this prompt to the model:

- "Given the following sentence: '[SENTENCE CONTAINING TARGET WORD]', what is the meaning of the word '[TARGET WORD]' in that context? Choose between {'[MEANING 1]', '[MEANING 2]', ... '[MEANING n]'}. You must assign each meaning a number from 0 to 4 where: {0: "cannot decide"; 1: "unrelated"; 2:"distantly related"; 3:"closely related"; 4: "identical"}."

The prompt was tested the first time on (8), where the target word is the adjective *beatus*, assigned more than one meaning in McGillivray et al. (2022) (Figure 4 below).

(8) [, *alterius mens rationibus agitandis exquirendisque alebatur cum oblectatione sollertiae, qui est unus suavissimus pastus animorum, alterius in caede et iniuriis cum et diurno et nocturno metu. Age confer Democritum Pythagoram, Anaxagoram: quae regna, quas opes studiis eorum et delectationibus antepones? Etenim, quae pars optima est in homine, in ea situm esse necesse est illud, quod quaeris, optimum. Quid est autem in homine sagaci ac bona mente melius?]* Eius bono fruendum est igitur, si beati esse volumus; bonum autem mentis est virtus; ergo hac **beatam** vitam contineri necesse est. [Hinc omnia quae pulchra honesta praeclara sunt, ut supra dixi, sed dicendum idem illud paulo uberius videtur, plena gaudiorum sunt. Ex perpetuis autem plenisque gaudiis cum perspicuum sit vitam beatam existere, sequitur ut ea

existat ex honestate. Sed ne verbis solum attingamus ea quae volumus ostendere, proponenda quaedam quasi moventia sunt, quae nos magis ad cognitionem intelligentiamque convertant. Sumatur enim nobis quidam praestans vir optumis artibus, isque animo parumper et cogitatione fingatur. Primum ingenio eximio sit necesse est; tardis enim mentibus virtus non]

'[...] If we want to be happy, we must enjoy the good of such a mind; however, the good of the mind is virtue: for this reason, a happy life is necessarily bound up with it. [...].'
(Cicero, Tusculanae, 46 BCE)

For the specific case of (8), ChatGPT was given this prompt.

- (9) Given the following sentence: "*alterius mens rationibus agitandis exquirendisque alebatur cum oblectatione sollertiae, qui est unus suavissimus pastus animorum, alterius in caede et iniuriis cum et diurno et nocturno metu. Age confer Democritum Pythagoram, Anaxagoram: quae regna, quas opes studiis eorum et delectationibus antepones? Etenim, quae pars optima est in homine, in ea situm esse necesse est illud, quod quaeris, optimum. Quid est autem in homine sagaci ac bona mente melius? Eius bono fruendum est igitur, si beati esse volumus; bonum autem mentis est virtus; ergo hac **beatam** vitam contineri necesse est. Hinc omnia quae pulchra honesta praeclara sunt, ut supra dixi, sed dicendum idem illud paulo uberius videtur, plena gaudiorum sunt. Ex perpetuis autem plenisque gaudiis cum perspicuum sit vitam beatam existere, sequitur ut ea existat ex honestate. Sed ne verbis solum attingamus ea quae volumus ostendere, proponenda quaedam quasi moventia sunt, quae nos magis ad cognitionem intelligentiamque convertant. Sumatur enim nobis quidam praestans vir optumis artibus, isque animo parumper et cogitatione fingatur. Primum ingenio eximio sit necesse est; tardis enim mentibus virtus non*" what is the meaning of the word "*beatam*" in that context? Choose between {"blessed", "rich"; "fortunate"; "happy"; "rewarded"}. You must assign each meaning a number from 0 to 4 where: {0: "cannot decide"; 1: "unrelated"; 2:"distantly related"; 3:"closely related"; 4: "identical"}."

This prompt did not produce the expected result, as the model's reply was:

- (10) In the given context, the most suitable meaning for the word "*beatam*" is "happy." Therefore, the assignment would be: "happy" corresponds to 4 ("identical").

We then tried to make the prompt more explicit:

- "Given the following sentence: '[SENTENCE CONTAINING TARGET WORD]', what is the meaning of the word '[TARGET WORD]' in that context? Choose between {'[MEANING 1]', '[MEANING 2]', ... '[MEANING n]'}. You must assign each meaning a number from 0 to 4 where: {0: "cannot decide"; 1: "unrelated"; 2:"distantly related"; 3:"closely related"; 4: "identical"}. You must mention all the possible meanings. Output the answer as a python dictionary, assigning a number 0-4 to each of the possible meanings."

This time, the model correctly understood its task and produced the Python dictionary shown in Figure 3.

```
python Copy code
{
  "blessed": 4,
  "rich": 0,
  "fortunate": 3,
  "happy": 4,
  "rewarded": 0
}
```

Figure 3. Output of the model for the meaning of *beatam* in (8) after giving it the prompt in (9).

Compare the results to the manual annotation (Figure 4 below).

blessed	rich	fortunate	happy	rewarded
1	2	3	4	2

Figure 4. Human annotation of the meaning of *beatam* in (8) (McGillivray et al. 2022).

The model identified the correct meaning of *beatam* in context, assigning the value 4 (identical to 'happy'). 'Fortunate' received 3 (closely related), as in the manual annotation. 'Blessed' was assigned 4 too, but this probably depends on the ambiguity of the English *blessed*. In Princeton WordNet (Miller et al. 1990; Fellbaum 1998; Miller and Fellbaum 2007), *blessed* is attributed six different synsets (Figure 5).

Adjective

- **S: (adj) blessed, blest** (highly favored or fortunate (as e.g. by divine grace)) "*our blessed land*"; "*the blessed assurance of a steady income*"
- **S: (adj) Blessed** (worthy of worship) "*the Blessed Trinity*"
- **S: (adj) blasted, blame, blamed, blessed, damn, damned, darned, deuced, goddam, goddamn, goddamned, infernal** (expletives used informally as intensifiers) "*he's a blasted idiot*"; "*it's a blamed shame*"; "*a blame cold winter*"; "*not a blessed dime*"; "*I'll be damned (or blessed or darned or goddamned) if I'll do any such thing*"; "*he's a damn (or goddam or goddamned) fool*"; "*a deuced idiot*"; "*an infernal nuisance*"
- **S: (adj) beatified, blessed** (Roman Catholic; proclaimed one of the blessed and thus worthy of veneration)
- **S: (adj) blessed** (enjoying the bliss of heaven)
- **S: (adj) blessed** (characterized by happiness and good fortune) "*a blessed time*"

Figure 5. Synsets attributed to the adjective *blessed* in Princeton WordNet.

In the prompt given to ChatGPT, 'blessed' is intended as 'Roman Catholic; proclaimed one of the blessed and thus worthy of veneration', as it also appears from (7). In the context of (8), ChatGPT probably interpreted 'blessed' as 'characterized by happiness and good fortune'. This is why it received a score of 4, as for 'happy' (Figure 3). More interestingly, the model did

not assign 1 (unrelated) or 2 (distantly related) to any of the meanings of *beatam*. Rather, it used 0 (cannot decide) for 'rich' and 'rewarded', which were assigned 2 (distantly related) in the manual annotation (Figure 4).

We tested ChatGPT asking it why it could not decide for 'rich' and 'rewarded', therefore why it assigned them a value of 0. The reply is given in (11).

- (11) In the given context, the words "rich" and "rewarded" are less directly related, and the context emphasizes aspects related to happiness, well-being, and virtue. Therefore, I assigned a value of 0, indicating that there isn't strong evidence in the context to decisively associate the meanings "rich" and "rewarded" with the word "*beatam*" in this particular passage.

From the output in (11), it seems that the model should have assigned 1 (unrelated) to 'rich' and 'rewarded'. However, the model assigned 0 (cannot decide) given the lack of strong evidence in the context «to decisively associate the [two] meanings» with the target word.

Overall, it seems that ChatGPT is capable of performing graded semantic annotation. When it is not triggered by the ambiguity of an English meaning, the model can identify the correct meaning of the word in context, assigning it a value of 4. If a meaning received a lower score in the human annotation, it can be assigned 0, as the model notices lack of strong evidence in the context and therefore it is not able to decide.

5. Issues

One of the parameters used by ChatGPT is the so-called "temperature", which controls the randomness of the model's output. The parameter ranges from 0 (more focused and deterministic output) to 1 (more diverse and creative output), and it is usually set on 0.5 in the free version of ChatGPT.

We have conducted analyses both with temperature set on 0, and with the standard 1 temperature. When the parameter is set on 1 and the model is given the same prompt for the same target word in the same text snippet, its replies may radically change. Three different tests on the model with the prompt given in (1), performed within a few seconds one from the other, led to three different outputs: (i) {0:" honor, repute, esteem"}, (ii) {2:"anything given as a mark of honor, an honorary gift, a reward"}, (iii) {1:"Public honor, official dignity, office, post,"}. We performed a preliminary test dividing our sample into two parts, one with 149 and one with 150 text snippets and we set temperature=0 and temperature=1 for the first and second subset respectively. A quantitative analysis of the model's performance with temperature=0 and temperature=1 is shown in figure 6 below. We can see how results differ when changing the model's temperature. As the lemmas in the two sets were different, however, part of the observed difference in performance can be attributed to the individual lemmas and the model's difficulty in performing their disambiguation, rather than to the temperature parameter itself. In general, it seems that adding randomness by setting the temperature value to 1 does not worsen results and, in fact, when considering nouns and adjectives this setting outperforms the deterministic setting of 0 temperature. This should be investigated with further experiments.

Related to the problem of stochasticity in the results is the fact that, even when the temperature is set to 0, in some cases the output is different from what is actually asked (i.e.

a python list). This can lead to complications in the automatic processing of multiple examples. We have dealt with this kind of issue by applying a post-processing step, where any non-conformant output is converted in the required format by matching the output to the closest meaning definition.

Figure 6: Accuracy of the model on the subset of text snippets with temperature=0 (150, marked in blue) and temperature=1 (149, marked in blue). The results have been divided by POS to account for different accuracies due to POS (see figure 2). The compared lemmas, however, are different and this may explain part of the difference in these results.

6. Author contributions

AF: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

IG: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

BMcG: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Appendix

Metadata	Left context	target word	right context	evil intent, wrongdoing	deceit, deception	fault	pain
Godfrey of Winchester, Epigrammata , cent. 12 A. D., cent. 12 A. D., poetry, Mediaevalis	, ac trutinat. De puero prodire senem me praecipis, at tu De vetulo esse puer, Maximiane, cupis. Esse semel puerum naturae non vetat ordo, Si superaddideris hoc venit ex vitio. Nominis et famae per secula longa petitor, Insiliit mediis ignibus Empedocles. Istius erroris dignus successor et haeres, Quaeque per alta ruens diceris, Hermenades. De dubia surgens c; na, Getulice, palles, Perdunt officium perdita membra suum. Esca quidem simplex sanum facit atque valentem, Sed sanum multi destituere cibi. Multimodis, Daciane,	dolis	evertis amicos, Fudera rescindens dissocias socios. Assuis adversos sub amoris glutine falso; Bella movens, pacem dissicis atque fidem.	3: Closely Related	4: Identical	1: Unrelated	1: Unrelated

Table 1: Example annotation of a text snippet for the target lemma *dolus* from McGillivray et al. (2021).